

THE INFLUENCE OF THE DISPERSION QUALITY OF CARBON NANOTUBES IN AN EPOXY MATRIX ON THE ELECTRICAL CONDUCTIVITY OF THE COMPOSITE

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SUMMARY

The electrical percolation threshold (PT) of carbon nanotube/epoxy composites can be adjusted over two orders of magnitude by controlling the dispersion quality. The dispersions were processed either solely with a dissolver disk or additionally with a three roll calender. The minimum PT is not necessarily linked with the state of the best dispersion.

Keywords: Carbon Nanotubes; Epoxy Matrix; Electrical Properties; Network Formation; Percolation; Mechanical Shearing

INTRODUCTION

Our previous work addressed the influence of shear forces on the dispersion quality and conductivity improvement in carbon nanotube filled epoxy matrix systems [1-3]. Here we show that it is possible to adjust the percolation threshold (PT) over two orders of magnitude only by controlling the dispersion quality, and that not the best dispersion quality is giving the lowest PT as might be expected.

MATERIALS AND EXPERIMENTAL DETAILS

Multi-wall carbon nanotubes were produced in house via aerosol chemical vapour deposition (ACVD). Details of the production methods can be found in [4-6]. The nanotubes grow straight away from the substrates and, therefore, are non-entangled and well aligned (see Fig. 1). Typical values for length, diameter and aspect ratio are 50 μm /80 nm/625. The polymer matrix consisted of bisphenol-A-based epoxy resin (Araldite LY 556) with an amine-based hardener (XB 3473) and was obtained from Huntsman Advanced Materials (Belgium). Samples of nanotube epoxy composites of varying filler concentrations were produced via a master batch process [2]. This involves dispersing the highest possible concentration of nanotubes into the epoxy resin with a dissolver disk rotating at 2000 rpm for 2 h at room temperature. The resulting suspension was poured into two bottles. The suspension of the second bottle was then processed with a three roll calender [7]. These samples were labelled with *calender*. Approximately 7 g of each suspension was poured into a vial and the appropriate amount of hardener was added (23:100 parts per weight of hardener:resin). Each suspension with hardener was stirred for 5 min, centrifuged at 3500 rpm for 1 min (to remove air bubbles) and then poured into four cavities (15 mm diameter, 5 mm depth) located inside a PTFE block. This block ensured a homogeneous heat-up process in order to avoid any convection, which would cause shearing and thus uncontrolled nanotube re-agglomeration.

Unintended shearing during sample preparation (stirring of hardener, pouring etc) however did not produce any visible agglomerates if the suspension temperature was lower than 50 °C.

Fig. 1 SEM images of (a) ACVD-aligned-grown and (b), for comparison, CCVD-aligned-grown multi-wall carbon nanotubes investigated in [3]. Typical lengths/diameters/aspect ratios of the nanotubes are (a) 50 µm/80 nm/625 and (b) 100 µm/12 nm/8300, respectively.

The block was heated to 100 °C, and then the suspensions of two cavities were manually sheared for 5 min at 60 rpm (the conductivity results were later averaged and referred to as the *slow stir* samples). The suspensions in the other two cavities were left untouched; therefore, they are referred to as the *no-stir* samples (again with averaged conductivities). Finally, the samples were cured in an oven at 120 °C. The filler concentration in the initial bottles was then lowered adding pure resin and again stirring for 30 min at 2000 rpm. Then the process described above was repeated again and again. After curing, the samples were removed from the cavities, polished and contacted for conductivity measurements by coating with conductive silver paint and contacted for conductivity measurements. Electrical measurements were performed in AC mode using an HP 4284A *LCR* meter at room temperature with voltage amplitude of 1.4 V over a frequency range from 20 Hz to 1 MHz. The AC conductivities were calculated from the admittance values and, being constant up to at least 1 kHz, the values at 100 Hz were considered to be DC equivalent. For optical analyses the samples were later polished down to a thickness of 0.2 mm.

INFLUENCE OF CALENDERING

In the first set of experiments ACVD-aligned-grown nanotubes were used and the sample preparation method was varied. The suspension was processed with a dissolver disk and partly calendered thereafter. The suspensions were then partly exposed to slow shearing and partly left unagitated. The conductivities of the resulting four sample sets are plotted in Fig 2.

Fig. 2 Log–Log plot of conductivity vs. nanotube weight fraction for the four sample preparation methods.

The sample set that was not calendered and not sheared exhibits a percolation threshold $\Phi_C = 0.09$ wt%, which – according to statistical percolation theory [8], $\Phi_C^{vol} \approx (2r)^{-1}$ or $\Phi_C^{wt} \approx r^{-1}$ (Φ_C^{vol} being the percolation threshold measured in vol% and Φ_C^{wt} the one measured in wt%) – indicates that the nanotubes should have a mean aspect ratio $r \approx 1000$. Since this is indeed the initial aspect ratio of the nanotubes we conclude that the observed/apparent percolation threshold is equal to the statistical/intrinsic value of the percolating system [2, 9]. According to these results and the optical micrographs in Fig. 3, the dissolver disk is able to optimally disperse aligned-grown nanotubes and the PTFE block really prevents convection and thus nanotube re-agglomeration. As soon as nanotube re-agglomeration is induced by modest shear forces the conductivity starts increasing (Figs. 2 and 3). This effect will be analysed in detail in the following sections. We now proceed to the discussion of the calendered sample set that was not stirred slowly. A percolation threshold can hardly be determined in this case; one of two samples always exhibits insulating behaviour for nearly all nanotube concentrations. Unfortunately, the second sample with 1 wt% of nanotubes cracked when removing it from the PTFE block cavity, but the other sample was insulating even at this high concentration. The statistical percolation threshold of this sample set seems to be located above 0.6 wt%, maybe even above 1 wt%. We can imagine two reasons for such a finding. The three roll calender could be able to separate the nanotubes and sheath them with a layer of insulating matrix more efficiently than the dissolver disk [7]. The matrix layer could then be too thick (>2 nm) to allow tunnelling conduction between adjacent nanotubes even at concentrations above 0.6 wt%.

Fig. 3 Optical micrographs of samples from each preparation method (columns) and varying CNT concentration (rows).

Charge contrast SEM analyses [10] seem to support this conclusion as it was not possible to produce a contrast between conducting and insulating regions in the calender + no-stir samples, while it was possible in all other samples (Fig. 4). This would mean that having the best nanotube dispersion quality is not favourable for electrical conductivity applications. The second reason could be the fracturing of nanotubes during the calendaring process. This could have lowered their aspect ratio and thereby increased their statistical percolation threshold. To verify this assumption we estimate the hydrodynamic forces exerted on the nanotubes during calendaring.

Fig. 4 Charge contrast SEM images of (a) slow stir, (b) no-stir, (c) calender + slow stir and (d) calender + no-stir samples containing 0.63 wt% ACVD-aligned-grown nanotubes.

We select a set-up where a single nanotube is clamped on one end while the hydrodynamic force F^{hyd} acts as a line load on it. This set-up definitely overestimates the real forces on a single nanotube suspended in the matrix. At the same time it represents an underestimation for the concentrated master batch suspension because interactions with other nanotubes are not considered. The resulting bending moment M is then defined as

$$M = \frac{l}{2} F^{hyd} = \frac{l}{2} \eta \dot{\gamma} d = \frac{\eta \dot{\gamma}^2 d}{2}$$

with the matrix viscosity $\eta = 10$ Pa s, nanotube length $l = 50$ μm and nanotube diameter $d = 80$ nm. The highest shear rate $\dot{\gamma} = 300\,000$ s^{-1} is found within the 5 μm gap of the calender rolls (the fastest rotating at 180 rpm, all having a diameter of 120 mm) [11]. With the second moment of area $I = \pi d^4/64$ for a nanotube with negligible inner diameter (as checked by TEM analyses), the resulting tensile stress in the outer layer of our multi-wall nanotube is

$$\frac{M}{I} \frac{d}{2} = \frac{16\eta\dot{\gamma}l^2}{\pi d^2} = \frac{16\eta\dot{\gamma}}{\pi} r^2 = 6\text{TPa}$$

This tensile stress exceeds the experimentally determined tensile strengths for the outer layer of a multi-wall nanotube (11–63 GPa [12]) as well as the nanotube fracture stress derived from molecular mechanics simulations (80 GPa [13]) by two orders of magnitude. It seems that our nanotubes could have easily been fractured in the calender. In order to support this conclusion, we perform a second estimate based on simulation results of fibres in a viscous fluid subjected to a laminar shear flow [14]. Yamamoto *et al* derived a condition for fibre fracture as a result of the bending stress imparted by the fluid after bending deformation of a fibre with Young's modulus E and aspect ratio r :

$$\frac{\eta\dot{\gamma}}{E} \approx 100 \frac{\ln(2r) - 1.75}{2r^4}$$

Young's moduli of 270–950 GPa [12] yield values between 10^{-6} and 10^{-5} for the left side of the equation, while an aspect ratio $r = 625$ yields 10^{-9} for the right side. According to this estimate, the bending stress exceeds the nanotube Young's modulus by three to four orders of magnitude, again indicating nanotube breakage. But to what extent does the calender break the nanotubes? A statistical percolation threshold of 0.6 – 1 wt% suggests the final aspect ratio to be around 60. This indicates a decrease of r by one order of magnitude. Interestingly, with this reduction in aspect ratio both estimated stresses – the tensile (being proportional to r^2) as well as the bending none (being proportional to r^4) – would decrease below the respective critical value for nanotubes and thus would stop breaking them. This could be a new method for adjusting the length of nanotubes in a composite with a calender. Further investigations are however necessary to support these statements. From now on, only non-calendered sample sets are discussed; therefore, we will not explicitly mention their processing method when referring to them.

INFLUENCE OF SHEAR FORCES ON PERCOLATION THRESHOLD AND ON MAXIMUM CONDUCTIVITY

The potential of shear forces to significantly lower the percolation threshold has been demonstrated in [2]. There, highly entangled nanotubes produced by a CCVD process (with a fixed-bed reactor) and provided by Nanocyl SA (Belgium) were used. The sample preparation method was very similar to the one discussed here. The percolation thresholds Φ_C of the no-stir samples coincide with values expected for statistically distributed particles of the respective aspect ratio: $\Phi_C^{nr} \approx r^{-1}$ [8]. The Nanocyl and the ACVD nanotubes both have $r \approx 600$ –1000 and $\Phi_C \approx 0.08$ wt% while for the CCVD-aligned grown nanotubes we find $r \approx 8300$ and $\Phi_C \approx 0.01$ wt%. These seem to be the statistical percolation thresholds of the composites. These thresholds can be further lowered through shear forces, giving rise to lower, kinetic percolation thresholds. Most interestingly, the factors between statistical and kinetic percolation thresholds are rather similar for all three nanotube types regardless of their huge differences in aspect ratio and entanglement state [3]. Thus, the influence of the aspect ratio on the kinetic percolation threshold is dominating the influence of shearing. This

conclusion is in contradiction to results presented in [15], where shorter nanotubes are found to have a lower kinetic percolation threshold than longer nanotubes of the same thickness. Comparing nanotubes of similar aspect ratios (ACVD-aligned-grown and Nanocyl), we conclude that the entanglement state is influencing neither the kinetic nor the statistical percolation thresholds. For the ACVD-aligned-grown nanotubes shearing seems to increase the conductivity by one to two orders of magnitude. Further experiments are necessary to confirm this finding and to assess the role of the nanotube thickness – being the only parameter that differs from both other nanotube types.

RHEOLOGICAL ANALYSES

So far, shear forces were exerted by the standard mixing equipment, a dissolver disk. It produces a rather complicated shear state in the suspension which is hard to analyse. Controlled shear states are found in a rheometer, which is most suitable for analysing the influence of shear forces on the network formation of CNT in a polymer.

Rheological properties were measured with a stress controlled rheometer (StressTech HR Fluid Rheometer) from REOLOGICA Instruments AB, Sweden, with 30 mm parallel plates and gap sizes between 0.5 and 1.3 mm. The lower plate is made of quartz glass and allows looking inside the gap using an optical microscope which is attached to a digital camera system.

For the optical analyses, a suspension of 0.05 wt% Nanocyl CNT in epoxy was produced following the routine described in [3]. The routine however was stopped before adding the hardener to the suspension. Instead, 1 ml of the suspension was transferred to the rheometer, heated to a constant temperature and then exposed to various shear rates. Images of the suspension were taken during the shearing process with the built-in optical microscope of the rheometer every 30 seconds. Each image could later be related to a certain shearing condition by the time stamps of both, the images and the shearing program.

Figure 5, left part, illustrates the built-up of agglomerates while the suspension is sheared with 0.1 and later with 1 s⁻¹. A shear rate of 10 s⁻¹ however seems to be already too high for the established agglomerates, they start decomposing into smaller ones. Increasing the shear rate to 100 s⁻¹ instantaneously decreases the agglomerates sizes even more. Figure 5, right part, displays what happens if the shear rate is now decreased again. At 10 s⁻¹ the agglomerates gather together to form bigger ones which – interestingly – match the size of the agglomerates from Figure 5, left part, at the end of their 10 s⁻¹ shearing (which was a destructive shear process). Further lowering of the shear rate to 1 and later 0.1 s⁻¹ reassembles the agglomerates to sizes found in Figure 5, left part, at the end of the respective shear conditions. This finding proves the agglomeration process to be reversible.

It is important to note that the estimation of the maximum shear rate exerted by the dissolver disk used in the experiments amounts to ~ 1 s⁻¹ when rotating with 50 rpm. This rotational speed proved to form agglomerates efficiently while 2000 rpm did not. As reported in the previous paragraph, 1 s⁻¹ is the maximum shear rate that is able to build up agglomerates in a rheometer and it perfectly coincides with the shear rate from the estimation.

Figure 5, left part: Images taken in situ while shearing a 0.05 wt% Nanocyl CNT/epoxy suspension with stepwise increasing shear rates at 70°C.

Figure 5, right part: Images taken in situ while shearing the suspension from the state obtained in Figure 5, left part, with stepwise decreasing shear rates at 70°C.

The width of each image is 1 mm.

CONCLUSION

It seems that the extremely high shear forces inside a calendar are able to separate the nanotubes efficiently and to sheath them with a thick layer of insulating matrix, which deteriorates the electrical performance of the composite. At the same time, the nanotubes are most probably broken down to an aspect ratio of ~ 60 , as is indicated by the position of the statistical percolation threshold.

The influence of shear forces on the electrical properties of a composite can only be assessed in comparison with a setup where shear forces (e.g. through convection or extrusion) can be completely excluded. Taking care of this, we find for all nanotube types a comparable influence of shear forces on the kinetic percolation threshold. In contradiction to [15], nanotubes with higher aspect ratios were found to have lower percolation thresholds. While the entanglement state of the nanotubes does not influence the kinetic or statistical percolation threshold, it (or the higher aspect ratio) seems to increase the conductivities considerably at high nanotube concentrations. In contrast to this, shearing was not able to increase the conductivities at high concentrations.

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